

SOCIO-ECONOMIC STATUS OF WOMEN IN GANIGA COMMUNITY

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Abstract

The time has come where both in the developing and advanced countries there is a need to study the factors which retard or accelerate social change. In the developing countries overweighed with age-old and unexamined traditions with the attendant consequences of confusion and cultural inertia it is imperative that scientific study be directed to the problem of social change. In India, we are presently passing through a crucial period of social change as never before. Old social order is being challenged by the new modes of life. Serious efforts to study the Ganiga community have not been made so far. The community which has been traditionally following the oil squeezing occupation has changed over to different occupations because of the changes that have been coming out in society. Significantly large population of Ganigas is concentrated in Karnataka and hence the need was felt to study the community and various changes which are affecting this community. The Ganiga community is treated as backward class, by the State which enjoys certain benefits sanctioned by the State and Central Government. In general the word backward class includes several communities based on certain criteria and are given certain benefits by the state.

Key words ; Ganigas, oil, Industry, status, socio-economic, Status Etc..

Introduction

India is a Country of Pluralism or Multi culture. The society is moving with its own History because it has so many communities in its womb. In a conventional society we can see many communities are preserving their identities. Many communities are following the same norms and conventions but some are undergone investable traditional changes in the modernized world. Among those Ganiga Community is the one which is trying to retain its originality. Ganiga community identified with its Occupation not by its caste. It is moving along with its occupation and preserved its uniqueness. We can also find women also contributed a lot and worked hard in this profession. Now we have to study how these women find an alternative profession when this occupation was far away and ganas meant only for pooja ceremony. Not only this, but also to find how to find the footsteps of this occupation based communities. It is necessary for us to study the past and present condition of these women and also the life which they have lead in all these years. It is also necessary for us to recall and narrate the story of the life of these communities lived. How once a rich community, which stepped along with cows, extracted pure oil, maintained its purity for the sake of people's health and lead its life when they stepped out of their traditional occupation and tried to retain its identity. And this study aims at specially the women who encountered the modern age and the changes followed by it.

Orgion Of The Word Ganiga

The word Ganiga is derived from two words Gana and Ega. The Ganiga word is formed by adding suffix ega to the word gana. The people who involved in this profession are called Ganigas. Ganigas claims that they belong to Suryavamsha. They found in all parts of India.

Hypothesis of the Study

Ganiga Community Women are leading socio-economically good life.

The Ganiga Community women are dependent on Conventional occupation.

Purpose of the Study

There are many communities in Karnataka itself. Although originally made of oil, these groups do not blend into each other's blood today. After the Industrial Revolution, it became necessary for the Ganiga community to move away from their original occupations. His knowledgeable heritage was defeated in front of large oil producing factories. The question is how this community has retained its socio cultural identity in such a dilemma. Some people in this community today, even in the smallest degree, are working with the oil fields. However, most people come out of their origins and engage in different jobs. This study aims to see whether the community has preserved or transformed its heritage from these shifts in the Ganiga community.

The purpose of this paper is to study Ganiga women who were settled in various geographical areas as Sajjana ganiga, jyothi ganiga, kariganiga, enneganiga.

Main purpose is to identify the social, economic, status of ganiga community women and to encounter them with contemporary social situations. To identify the barriers that is in the empowerment of Ganiga community women.

Review of Literature

Thomas Georgea, K R Rajanib, 2018, Lingayts of Karnataka: A Twelfth Century Social and Religious Reforming Movement in Hinduism, Online International Interdisciplinary Research Journal, {Bi-Monthly}, ISSN 2249-9598, Volume-08, Nov 2018, Special Issue, 02. in this Articals mentions the Ganiga caste, Oil Pressers (Ganiga) - "A subgroup of the Lingayat, the Ganiga are distributed in the

Belgaum, Bidar, Nijapur, Nellary, Dharwad, Chitradurga, Gulbarga and Raichur districts of Karnataka. The Kannada term aniga means oil presser, and has been derived from the term gana or oil crusher. Though the traditional occupation of the Ganiga Lingayat is oil pressing, they are also engaged in agriculture, animal husbandry, business, trade, service, self-employment and wage-labour. A traditional caste council exists among them, headed by a daivantharu" (Thomas Georgea, K R Rajanib:2018:235-236).

[http://www.oijrj.org/oijrj/nov2018-special-issue\(02\)/33.pdf](http://www.oijrj.org/oijrj/nov2018-special-issue(02)/33.pdf)

Janaki Ramaiah, G, 1996,"Social Change among the Gandlas" In Chittoor District, Ph.d Thesis Submitted by Venkateswara University, Tirupathi. The people belonging to this community are called as "GANIGA" in Kannada Correspondingly in Telugu they are called "GANDL" and in Tamil as VANIYANS The name GANIGA is derived from the word "GANUGA" meaning an oil mill This caste is divided into three sub sections None of them interdine nor intermarries with others Ganiga further occurs as an occupational name for Lingayat oil vendors, and for Mogers who are employed as oil-pressers. The "GANDLAS are subdivided into HEGGANIGAS who yoke two oxen to a stone oil mill, "KIRGANIGA" and squeeze oil from oil seeds by crushing them in the motor The other one is "ONTIYEDDU GANIGA", where one animal is used for crushing and squeezing oil They are

collectively known as "JOTI PANS", or "JOTI NAGARAMS" The GANDALS are identified with different names in different regions In Coastal Andhra, they are called as "TELIKILA" and in Telangana they are called as DEVAGANDLA and in Rayalaseema they are called as GANDLAS" The sub sectlon 'Ontiyeddu Ganigas' are again sub divided into 'Devaganigas' and 'Sayyanaganigas' Even these two sub sections are not allowed to Interdine or Intermarry" (Janaki Ramaiah G:1996:16). (<http://hdl.handle.net/10603/70878>).

Scope

The scope of a study explains the extent to which the research area will be explored n the work. As a researcher we have to define our scope or area of focus. For this we have chosen the ganiga community women in selected villages of various districts.

Research Methodology

Fundamentally it is a descriptive and analytical study. Secondary sources like Interview, Questionnaire, and participatory research are followed to get the information. Status Of Women In Ganiga Community Ganiga women are not only performed their House hold chores but also involved in the extraction of oil from the Ganas which are the back bone of their houses. Social Status Man is a Social animal. While living in society he has to live with the societal norms and ways. In the same ways he has follow norms and ways in family also.

SL NO	SUB CASTES	FAMILIES	PATRIARCHAL	MATRIARCHAL	PERCENTAGE
1	SAJJANA GANIGA	30	25	05	63.83
2	JYOTHI GANIGA	11	09	02	23.41
3	KARE GANIGA	02	02	-	4.25
4	ENNE GANIGA	04	04	-	8.51
5	TOTAL	47	40	07	
	TOTAL PERCENTAGE		85.10	14.90	100%

TABLE: 1.1. FAMILY SYSTEM OF GANIGAS

Pie Chart: 1.1.1 Family Distribution of Ganigas

Patriarchal Family system is practiced in Ganigas and its sub castes. In the above chart patriarchal system is in 25 families of Sajjana Ganigas and 05 Families are practicing Matriarchal Family system. Men are the Head of the families before the Matriarchy. Women in the family had to inevitably held the responsibility of the Family after the Death Men, who are the head of the families. In Matriarchal Family system Woman is the head and prominence is given to her in all the familial matters and accounts (Kavitha Rai:2007:28). Many Sociologists like Spencer, Taylor, Morgan Brie fault

called it as “Matriarchal Family system because Woman’s role in the birth, growth and nurturing of the child”(Hirematha S J:1995-96:31-32). In Jyothi Ganigas 9 families are practicing patriarchal and 02 families are practicing matriarchal Family system. In the same way Kare ganiga and enne ganigas are all practicing Patriarchal family system only. Matriarchal Family system is very less in Ganigas. Man, who is the head of the family manages everything. Nuclear and Joint Family is also there in them.

Table:1.2.1 Gender-wise educational level of surveyed Ganiga community

SL NO	EDUCATION LEVEL	MALE	FEMALE	TOTAL	TOTAL PERCENTAGE
1	PRIMARY	35	28	63	38.66
2	HIGH SCHOOL	25	22	47	28.84
3	PUC	12	07	19	11.65
4	GRADUATION	08	07	15	9.20
5	POST GRADUATION	05	03	08	4.90
6	ITI	08	03	11	6.75
	TOTAL	93	70	163	
	TOTAL PERCENTAGE	57.05	42.95		100

Pie Chart: 1.2. Gender-wise educational distribution of Ganiga community

In Table 1.2 , 6th to 8 is considered as Primary , 9th to 10th is high school and 11th to 12th is considers as PU Course. Later is called as Under Graduation, Post graduation and ITI. As per the Survey conducted in various parts of Karnataka total 63 children are studying in Middle School. In this 35 students are Boys and 28 are girls. From 8th to 10th in High school 47 students are studying. Among them 25 boys and 22 are girls. In PUC 12 boys and 07 girls, total 19 students are studying. 15 students are pursuing B.A. and B.Com. In this 08 Males and 07 Female students. Only 08 students are pursuing Post graduation. In this 05 boys and 03 girls. In ITI

08 boys and 03 girls are getting Technical Education. Through survey we can find Total 163 students are pursuing studies. Among this 93 are boys and 70 are girls. 57.05 of Boys % and 42.95% of girls are getting Education. The main thing about this is, though 25 boys and 18 girls total 43 students under the age of 0- 05 are studying in Primary they are not considered for Literacy (According to Indian Government). In the same way 43 students, the students who dropped their education in the primary level and those who can read only are not considered in the Table.

Economic Status

TABLE: 1.3.1 Gender wise occupation villages of surveyed Ganiga community

SL NO	OCCUPATION	MALE	FEMALE	TOTAL	TOTAL PERCENTAGE
1	AGRICULTURE	22	20	42	51.85
2	WAGE LABOUR	04	03	07	08.65
3	GOVERNMENT	06	02	08	9.88
4	PRIVATE	10	03	13	16.04
5	OTHER	08	03	11	13.58
	TOTAL	50	31	81	
	TOTAL PRCENTAGE	61.73	38.27		100

Pie Chart: 1.3. Gender-wise occupation of Ganiga community

For the study we have chosen 07 villages from the Ganiga Community in Kudligi Taluk of Vijayanagara District. Through Questionnaire method extracted the information of 47 families from 7 villages. 44 % of men and 64.51% of women are practising Agriculture as their basic occupation. Total percentage of me and women who are involved in this occupation are 51.85%. The percentage of Men who have chosen Agriculture as their occupation is 8% and the women are 9.67%. Total 8.65 % of men and women are in this occupation. 12% of men and 6.45% of women are POLITICAL STATUS

working in Government Sector. Total 9.88 % of Ganiga community members are in Government sector. Those who are working in private sector are 19.04 % in this 20% are Men and 9.67% are women. Other small trades and occupations are total 13.58 and in those 16% women and 9.67% are men. As ages passed this community adopted agriculture as Occupation. Nowadays the Educated are preferring Government Jobs. As the education of women is less, they are working as house maids. Most importantly the children who are under 6 to 17 age are not considered here for Occupation.

TABLE: 1.4.1 ABOUT THE RESERVATION CONVENIENCE FOR GANIGAS

SL NO	SUBCASTES	FAMILIES	GETTING	NOT	FOR	TOTAL PERCENTAGE
1	SAJANA GANIGAJ	30	14	10	06	63.83
2	JYOTHI GANIGA	11	05	03	.03	23.41
3	KAREGANIGA	02	01	01	-	4.25
4	ENNE GANIGA	04	-	04	-	8.51
	TOTAL	47	20	18	09	
	TOTAL PERCENTAGE		42.55	38.30	19.15	100

Chart: 1.4. RESERVATION CONVENIENCE FOR GANIGAS

Chart: 1.4. RESERVATION CONVENIENCE FOR GANIGAS

According to Sajjana Ganigas Government has given 2A Reservation for Ganigas. But to get that Reservation they need Caste and Income Certificate. But they are not getting that. Ten Families of Sajjana Ganigas are saying like that. Remaining 14 families of sajjana ganigas are doing petty job and getting education. And other 9 families are having the opinion that ‘we have reservation, but we try to get it’. And to get various facilities the reservation had helped them and some of them are satisfied with it. In jyotiganigas, 05 families are getting the reservation, and the 03 families are having the opinion that they are not having the reservation at all. And 03 families are okay with it. And they have also got some government facilities. In Kareganigsa only one family is getting the reservation and another one is not having anything. In the same way when we asked the 04 families of Enneganigas , they are saying they are not getting any of the government facilities. They don’t even have the Ration card, caste and income certificates. Though they have mentioned as Enne ganigas while admitting to the school also, we are not getting the caste and income certificates. We were extracting the oil from the ganas so are called as Enne ganigas. When they left the Gana occupation, for the sake of prestige and as our parents were not educated enough they have entered the caste as Lingayata. And we truly belong to Enne ganigas. So we are not getting the ganiga Reservation. Despite of all this we have mentioned our children’s caste as Ganigas. Because of this though we have all the facilities, we are unable to get this. “Government has decided this as Backward section based on its Educational, Social, Political, Economic condition. The population of this community is bit larger than any other backward community. The population has to mention in the Census. Then our Community people will get More number of Reserved seats.”(Jayabasava swamigalu: 2015:258)

Study Outcomes

1. Ganigas are distributed in Kudligi Taluk. Only one or Two Ganiga families are found in 4-5 villages. This is seen as scientific one means ganigas are stayed to sell and produce the oil for 4-5 villages.
2. Ganigas have left their traditional Occupation. Educated are not showing interest in this. And they don’t have strength to compete in this mechanical world. This is a unique occupation.
3. Matriarchal Family system is very less in Ganigas. Men manage the Familial affairs. They have both Joint and Nuclear Family. Nuclear Family is more in Ganigas.
4. In Kudligi, women in Sajjana Ganiga community are depended on Agriculture, Kare ganigas are doing small trades and Enneganiga’s women are selling oil till day.
5. Ganigas are facing problem in getting Caste and Income certificate. Ganigas facing difficulty to get 2a certificate, so they could not come to Politics.

Suggestions

The government and Community has to increase Reservation encourage as to encourage Ganiga women enter into politics. The Other Backward Welfare Commission has to make programs to make them self employees and independents. Government should economic aid to women to start small scale Industries and to provide Market for the Goods which they have produced. Society and Government has to identify the Children who are deprived of Education and encourage them to continue. Government has to instruct the Taluk Magistrate officers to get the Caste certificate easily and the Community has to pressurize the Government to do the same. Government has to identify the Traditional Compressed Oil Industries and protect them providing the Loan facilities.

Higher Education is helpful for the Psychological development, encourage the education of that community including women.

Conclusion

Totally women in Ganiga Community are struggling to get Higher education by facing all the hurdles and to live independently. They are practicing their traditional occupation and also doing small trades and occupations. And also trying to overcome the situations like dependency on men for money. They are expecting the support of family to enter the Politics. Along with this she is also trying to create her identity in the society by practicing the Compressed Oil Industry.

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